

Issue Tracker

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

Issue Tracker 2024/008
October 23rd, 2024

[Medicare pilot aims for \\$2 generic drugs](#): On October 9, the Biden administration released a list of 101 generic drugs that it plans to make available through Medicare at a cost of \$2 per month. Medicare is seeking feedback on the list ahead of the January 2027 pilot program implementation, which will be optional for Medicare prescription drug plans when it launches. While the future of the \$2/month program is dependent on the outcome of the November presidential election, all Medicare plans will have a universal cap of [\\$2,000 for prescription drugs](#) as of 2025.

[Pan-Canadian Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance: Year 1 Progress Report \(June 2023 to May 2024\)](#): The Public Health Agency of Canada (PHAC) released its Year 1 Progress Report outlining Canada's efforts to combat Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR). The report focuses on surveillance, infection prevention, research and innovation, and antimicrobial use stewardship. Achievements include improved data collection, increased collaboration across sectors, and public health awareness campaigns, though challenges remain, such as integrating data systems and ensuring sustainable funding for AMR initiatives.

[Liberal, NDP bill to cover diabetes and birth control medication receives royal assent](#): On October 10, Canada passed *The Pharmacare Act*, laying the foundation for a universal pharmacare program. The legislation allows the federal government to sign agreements with the provinces and territories to cover diabetes and birth control medication. Health Minister Mark Holland [publicly stated his intention](#) to have these agreements in place by spring 2025. The future expansion of the program to cover the cost of other drugs will be shaped by the outcome of the next federal election, which must be held on or before October 20, 2025.

[Cancer centers launch Cancer AI Alliance \(CAIA\) to unlock discoveries, transform care using cancer data and applied AI](#): The CAIA is a new collaboration between Dana-Farber, Fred Hutch, Memorial Sloan Kettering, and Johns Hopkins. Backed by over \$40 million in funding from AWS, Deloitte, Microsoft, and NVIDIA, CAIA will use AI to analyze large datasets from cancer centers, improving treatment outcomes, especially for rare cancers. Using federated AI learning, which keeps raw data private, CAIA will focus on overcoming key technical and regulatory challenges in cancer research, such as accessing computational power and ensuring data privacy. The alliance will begin producing insights by the end of 2025.

[FDA Perspective on the Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Health Care and Biomedicine](#): FDA Commissioner Robert Califf coauthored a paper calling for the adoption of flexible regulatory tools to keep pace with the development of AI-enabled

medical devices and treatments, with a particular focus on lifecycle performance monitoring to capture the evolving nature of AI models. Califf argues that a robust regulatory regime is necessary to maintain public trust in nascent AI-powered health innovations and to properly govern the tension between AI's potential to maximize financial returns and improve patient outcomes.